

Low-Complexity Decoupled Super-Resolution Sequential ToF-AoA Estimation for Bistatic ISAC OFDM

Luqi Yang

Department of Signal Theory and Communications
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Leganés, Spain
lyang@ing.uc3m.es

Víctor P. Gil Jiménez

Department of Signal Theory and Communications
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Leganés, Spain
vgil@ing.uc3m.es

Abstract—Integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) in bistatic configurations enables simultaneous user equipment (UE) self-localization and passive target positioning by leveraging multipath propagation. However, existing approaches for joint time-of-flight (ToF) and angle-of-arrival (AoA) estimation either incur prohibitive computational complexity in multi-carrier MIMO-OFDM systems or suffer from limited resolution due to Fourier grid constraints. In this paper, we introduce a low-complexity super-resolution framework that decouples the high-dimensional joint estimation problem into a sequence of tractable low-dimensional stages. Specifically, ToF is first estimated via one-dimensional ESPRIT in the frequency domain, followed by a zero-forcing temporal projection that isolates individual propagation paths. Subsequently, AoA is refined on a per-path basis using two-dimensional spatial ESPRIT. Both stages incorporate minimum description length (MDL) criteria for fully autonomous model order selection. The estimated ToF and AoA parameters are then mapped to the two-dimensional positions of the UE and passive targets through a closed-form bistatic geometric transformation. Complexity analysis reveals that the proposed method reduces computational cost by approximately three orders of magnitude compared to conventional joint 2D ESPRIT approaches, while preserving high-resolution capabilities. Monte Carlo simulations under 5G NR-compliant settings at 28 GHz demonstrate that the proposed framework achieves competitive positioning accuracy relative to 2D-FFT baselines.

Index Terms—Integrated Sensing and Communication, bistatic sensing, ESPRIT, MIMO-OFDM, joint UE and targets localization

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) has emerged as a promising technology for the next generation mobile networks, enabling simultaneous data transmission and environmental perception by leveraging the same temporal and spectral resources [1]. ISAC operates mainly through monostatic and bistatic sensing modes. Compared to monostatic sensing, bistatic sensing does not suffer from severe self-interference and has a wider sensing range and

reduced vulnerability to jamming [2]. In downlink bistatic sensing system, the Base Station (BS) serves as a transmitter and the User Equipment (UE) receives the transmitted signal via the Line of Sight (LoS) path. Besides, it also receives the reflections from passive targets in the environment through Non-LoS (NLoS) paths. By jointly extracting Time of Flight (ToF) and Angle of Arrival (AoA) information from each multipath component, the UE can estimate its own position and further localize targets in a single Multiple-Input Multiple-Output Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (MIMO-OFDM) transmission.

The joint estimation of ToF and AoA has been extensively studied previously in the literature. In 1998, van der Veen *et al.* [3] proposed a two-dimensional (2D) Estimation of signal parameters via rotational invariant techniques (ESPRIT)-like shift-invariance method to simultaneously estimate delay and angular parameters. This algorithm [3] constructs a Kronecker-structured observation matrix of dimension $L_f N_U$, where L_f is the frequency-domain smoothing aperture and N_U is the number of antennas at the UE. The resulting Eigenvalue Decomposition (EVD) has $\mathcal{O}((L_f N_U)^3)$ complexity, which becomes prohibitive for wideband OFDM systems with hundreds of subcarriers. Extensions based on CP decomposition [4] further improve accuracy by preserving multi-dimensional signal structure. Tensor-based methods [5] scale with the product of all array dimensions. The sparse Bayesian learning framework for bistatic mmWave MIMO radar [6] requires iterative matrix inversions proportional to the 3D grid size. All mentioned algorithms are computationally heavy, and more importantly, none have been evaluated in a bistatic MIMO-OFDM ISAC system. In contrast to the above methods, Digital Fourier Transform (DFT)-based algorithms have higher computational efficiency. Xiao *et al.* [7] developed DFT-based joint angle-range-velocity estimation for monostatic MIMO-OFDM ISAC, but the reliance on DFT processing inherently limits resolution to the Fourier-grid spacing. Other methods for increasing the accuracy in passive bistatic estimations have been proposed by authors in [8].

In this paper, a computationally efficient with super-

This research is partially supported by the European Union, through the Horizon Europe Marie Skłodowska-Curie Doctoral Networks Programme ISAC-NEWTON under Grant 101169496 and by Project SOFIA-AIR (PID2023-147305OB-C31) MICIU/10.13039/501100011033/AEI/EFDR/EU.

resolution algorithm is designed and evaluated in the Downlink bistatic MIMO-OFDM ISAC sensing system. The proposed framework has the following contributions:

- A **decoupled ToF-AoA estimation architecture** that reduces the dominant EVD from $\mathcal{O}((L_f N_U)^3)$ to $\mathcal{O}(L_f^3 + K \cdot L_s^3)$ via sequential 1D frequency ESPRIT, zero-forcing temporal projection, and per-path 2D spatial ESPRIT.
- **Autonomous model order detection** using the Minimum Description Length (MDL) criterion [9] at both ToF and AoA estimation stages, eliminating manual threshold tuning.
- **Bistatic geometric positioning** via closed-form transformation mapping paired ToF-AoA to 2D positions of the UE and the targets.
- **Comprehensive evaluation** under 5G NR parameters at 28 GHz, benchmarked against 2D-FFT baselines with numerical Cramér-Rao bound (CRB).

The remainder of this paper consists of four sections. Section II presents the bistatic MIMO-OFDM ISAC sensing system model. Section III presents the proposed decoupled super-resolution localization algorithm and demonstrates the reduced computation complexity against 2D joint ESPRIT. Section IV presents the simulation setups and results. Section V concludes the paper and suggests directions for future work.

This paper adopts the following notations. Regular letters denote scalars, bold lowercase letters denote vectors, and bold uppercase letters are used for Matrices. \mathbf{I}_N is an identity matrix of size $N \times N$. For a matrix \mathbf{A} , the notation $\mathbf{A}(a : b, c : d)$ denotes the submatrix formed by the intersection of rows a through b and columns c through d . Additionally, $\text{vec}(\mathbf{A})$ denotes the vectorization operator that stacks the columns of \mathbf{A} into a single column vector. \mathbf{A}^T and \mathbf{A}^H denote the transpose and Hermitian transpose operations of the matrix \mathbf{A} , respectively. Pseudoinverse of the matrix \mathbf{A} is denoted by \mathbf{A}^\dagger . Moreover, $\|(\cdot)\|$ is the Euclidean norm of a vector. Finally, $\mathbf{x} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$ denotes a zero-mean circularly symmetric random Gaussian vector with covariance σ^2 .

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Geometry and Channel Model

In Fig. 1, the scenario for the downlink bistatic MIMO-OFDM ISAC sensing system is shown. In this system, the carrier frequency f_c is set, without loss of generality to 28 GHz. The wavelength is $\lambda = c/f_c$. A BS equipped with an $N_{B,x} \times N_{B,y}$ Uniform Rectangular Array (URA) transmits OFDM signals over M subcarriers with spacing Δf and P pilot symbols. A UE equipped with an $N_{U,x} \times N_{U,y}$ URA receives the signal. The BS is at known position $\mathbf{p}_{BS} \in \mathbb{R}^2$, the UE at unknown \mathbf{p}_{UE} , and K_t passive targets at $\{\mathbf{p}_{t,k}\}_{k=1}^{K_t}$.

The multipath propagation involves a direct LoS path ($k=0$) and K_t NLoS paths reflected by the targets. The k -th path is characterized by delay τ_k , AoA ψ_k , angle of departure (AoD) θ_k , and complex channel gain β_k

$$\tau_0 = \|\mathbf{p}_{UE} - \mathbf{p}_{BS}\|/c, \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_k = (\|\mathbf{p}_{t,k} - \mathbf{p}_{BS}\| + \|\mathbf{p}_{UE} - \mathbf{p}_{t,k}\|)/c, \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Illustration of a downlink bistatic MIMO-OFDM ISAC sensing system, where the BS transmits pilot signals and the UE receives pilot signals and reflections from passive targets to localize itself and the targets.

with path gains derived from the free space (LoS) and bistatic radar (NLoS) models [10]

$$\beta_0 = e^{j\zeta_0} \frac{\lambda}{4\pi \|\mathbf{p}_{UE} - \mathbf{p}_{BS}\|}, \quad (3)$$

$$\beta_k = \sigma_{\text{RCS},k} e^{j\zeta_k} \frac{\lambda}{(4\pi)^{3/2} \|\mathbf{p}_{BS} - \mathbf{p}_{t,k}\| \|\mathbf{p}_{t,k} - \mathbf{p}_{UE}\|}, \quad (4)$$

where $\sigma_{\text{RCS},k}$ denotes the Radar Cross Section (RCS) of the k -th target and ζ_k is the k -th phase uniformly distributed over $[-\pi, \pi]$.

The MIMO channel at the m -th subcarrier ($m = 0, \dots, M-1$) is

$$\mathbf{H}[m] = \sum_{k=0}^{K_t} \beta_k e^{-j2\pi m \Delta f \tau_k} \mathbf{a}_U(\psi_k) \mathbf{a}_B^H(\theta_k), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{a}_U(\psi) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_U}$ and $\mathbf{a}_B(\theta) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_B}$ are URA steering vectors with $N_U = N_{U,x} N_{U,y}$ and $N_B = N_{B,x} N_{B,y}$.

B. Signal Model

The BS transmits a pilot matrix $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{s} \mathbf{1}_P^T \in \mathbb{C}^{N_B \times P}$, where the spatial precoder $\mathbf{s} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_B}} \mathbf{1}_{N_B} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_B}$ is applied uniformly to all M subcarriers and P OFDM symbols to ensure omnidirectional illumination of the sensing scene.

The raw received signal at the UE at the m -th subcarrier and p -th symbol is

$$\mathbf{y}[m, p] = \mathbf{H}[m] \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n}[m, p], \quad \mathbf{n}[m, p] \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_U}), \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{H}[m] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_U \times N_B}$ is the MIMO channel defined in (5). Since the precoder is identical across all P symbols, the noise is suppressed by coherent averaging

$$\bar{\mathbf{y}}[m] = \frac{1}{P} \sum_{p=1}^P \mathbf{y}[m, p] = \mathbf{H}[m] \mathbf{s} + \bar{\mathbf{n}}[m], \quad (7)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{n}}[m] \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \frac{\sigma_n^2}{P} \mathbf{I}_{N_U})$ is the residual noise after averaging, benefitting from a P -fold reduction in noise variance. Substituting (5), the u -th element of $\bar{\mathbf{y}}[m]$ can be expressed as follows

$$\bar{y}_u[m] = \sum_{k=0}^{K_t} \alpha_{u,k} e^{-j2\pi m \Delta f \tau_k} + \bar{n}_u[m], \quad (8)$$

where $\alpha_{u,k} = \beta_k [\mathbf{a}_U(\psi_k)]_u \mathbf{a}_B^H(\theta_k) \mathbf{s}$. Stacking across all N_U antennas yields the symbol-averaged received matrix $\bar{\mathbf{Y}} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_U \times M}$, which serves as the input to the proposed estimation framework in Section III.

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

Fig. 2 presents an overview of the proposed algorithm with sequential Frequency-Domain 1D ESPRIT for ToF, Zero-Forcing Temporal Projection, Per-Path 2D Spatial ESPRIT for AoA, and Geometric 2D positioning. The details of each stage are as follows.

A. Stage 1: Frequency-Domain 1D ESPRIT for ToF

For each UE antenna u , the received vector $\bar{\mathbf{y}}_u \in \mathbb{C}^M$ is divided into overlapping subarrays of length $L_f = \lfloor M/2 \rfloor$ to form a frequency smoothed covariance matrix [11]

$$\mathbf{R}_f = \frac{1}{K_f N_U} \sum_{u=1}^{N_U} \sum_{i=1}^{K_f} \bar{\mathbf{y}}_u^{(i)} (\bar{\mathbf{y}}_u^{(i)})^H, \quad (9)$$

where $K_f = M - L_f + 1$ and $\bar{\mathbf{y}}_u^{(i)} = [\bar{y}_u[i-1], \dots, \bar{y}_u[i+L_f-2]]^T$. The smoothing across both frequency subarrays and antennas decorrelates the coherent multipath components.

The number of resolvable paths, \hat{K} , is autonomously determined by minimizing the Minimum Description Length (MDL) criterion [9]. Let $q \in \{0, 1, \dots, L_f - 1\}$ denote the hypothesized number of signal paths. The MDL cost function evaluated at candidate q is computed using the sorted eigenvalues $\{\lambda_1 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_{L_f}\}$ of \mathbf{R}_f :

$$\text{MDL}(q) = (L_f - q) N_{\text{eff}} \ln \frac{\bar{\lambda}_q}{\tilde{\lambda}_q} + \frac{q(2L_f - q)}{2} \ln N_{\text{eff}}, \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{\lambda}_q$ and $\tilde{\lambda}_q$ denote the arithmetic and geometric means of the $L_f - q$ smallest eigenvalues, respectively, and $N_{\text{eff}} = K_f N_U$ is the effective number of snapshots. The final estimated number of paths is then extracted via $\hat{K} = \arg \min_q \text{MDL}(q)$.

Let $\mathbf{E}_s \in \mathbb{C}^{L_f \times \hat{K}}$ denotes the signal subspace. The ESPRIT [12] rotation matrix $\Phi_f = \mathbf{E}_1^\dagger \mathbf{E}_2$, formed from the shifted submatrices $\mathbf{E}_1 = \mathbf{E}_s(1:L_f-1,:)$ and $\mathbf{E}_2 = \mathbf{E}_s(2:L_f,:)$, yields delay estimates

$$\hat{\tau}_k = -\frac{\angle(z_k)}{2\pi\Delta f}, \quad k = 1, \dots, \hat{K}, \quad (11)$$

where $\{z_k\}$ are the eigenvalues of Φ_f .

B. Stage 2: Zero-Forcing Temporal Projection

With the estimated delays $\{\hat{\tau}_k\}$, we construct a delay steering matrix $\mathbf{A}_\tau \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times \hat{K}}$ with entries $[\mathbf{A}_\tau]_{m,k} = e^{-j2\pi m \Delta f \hat{\tau}_k}$. The per-path spatial snapshots are isolated via zero-forcing projection

$$\mathbf{X} = (\mathbf{A}_\tau^\dagger \bar{\mathbf{Y}}^T)^T, \quad \mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_U \times \hat{K}}, \quad (12)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{Y}} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_U \times M}$ is the symbol-averaged received signal matrix. Each column \mathbf{x}_k of \mathbf{X} contains the isolated spatial signature of the k -th path.

C. Stage 3: Per-Path 2D Spatial ESPRIT for AoA

For each resolved path k , the spatial snapshot \mathbf{x}_k is reshaped into $\mathbf{X}_{2D} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{U,y} \times N_{U,x}}$ corresponding to the URA geometry. 2D spatial smoothing is applied using subarrays of size $L_y \times L_x$

$$\mathbf{R}_{ss}^{(k)} = \frac{1}{K_y K_x} \sum_{i_x=1}^{K_x} \sum_{i_y=1}^{K_y} \mathbf{v}_{i_x, i_y} \mathbf{v}_{i_x, i_y}^H, \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_{i_x, i_y} = \text{vec}(\mathbf{X}_{2D}(i_y:i_y+L_y-1, i_x:i_x+L_x-1))$, $K_y = N_{U,y} - L_y + 1$, and $K_x = N_{U,x} - L_x + 1$. The MDL criterion is applied to the eigenvalues of $\mathbf{R}_{ss}^{(k)}$ to autonomously detect the number of AoA components per path. The 2D ESPRIT shift matrices Ψ_x and Ψ_y along the x - and y -axes of the subarray are jointly diagonalized to extract

$$\hat{\psi}_k = \text{atan2}(-\mu_{y,k}, -\mu_{x,k}), \quad (14)$$

where $\text{atan2}(y, x)$ denotes the four-quadrant inverse tangent function, and $\mu_{x,k}$ and $\mu_{y,k}$ are the phases of the diagonalized shift matrices.

D. Stage 4: Geometric 2D Positioning

The LOS path (smallest estimated delay) provides direct UE localization

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{\text{UE}} = \mathbf{p}_B - c\hat{\tau}_0 \begin{bmatrix} \cos \hat{\psi}_0 \\ \sin \hat{\psi}_0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

For the k -th NLOS path ($k \geq 1$), the total bistatic path length is $L_k = c\hat{\tau}_k$ and the angular separation at the UE is $\alpha_k = |\hat{\psi}_0 - \hat{\psi}_k|$. Using the law of cosines, the UE-to-target distance is

$$\hat{r}_k = \frac{L_k^2 - \hat{d}_0^2}{2(L_k - \hat{d}_0 \cos \alpha_k)}, \quad (16)$$

where $\hat{d}_0 = c\hat{\tau}_0$, and the target position is

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{t,k} = \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{\text{UE}} + \hat{r}_k \begin{bmatrix} \cos \hat{\psi}_k \\ \sin \hat{\psi}_k \end{bmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

E. Complexity Analysis

We compare the computational complexity of the proposed decoupled algorithm against the joint 2D ESPRIT baseline [3]. The joint approach stacks the frequency and spatial dimensions into a single observation vector of length $L_f N_U$. The dominant cost is the Eigenvalue Decomposition (EVD) of the $(L_f N_U) \times (L_f N_U)$ covariance matrix, giving $\mathcal{O}((L_f N_U)^3)$. In the proposed method, Stage 1 requires EVD of $\mathbf{R}_f \in \mathbb{C}^{L_f \times L_f}$ at cost $\mathcal{O}(L_f^3)$. Stage 2 costs $\mathcal{O}(M \hat{K}^2)$. Stage 3 requires \hat{K} EVD of size $L_s = L_x L_y$, each costing $\mathcal{O}(L_s^3)$. Table I summarizes the comparison.

Due to the prohibitive computational cost of the joint 2D ESPRIT ($\sim 4.5 \times 10^{10}$ flops per trial), it is excluded from the Monte Carlo evaluation and compared only via analytical complexity in Table I.

Fig. 2. Flowchart of the proposed decoupled MDL-ESPRIT bistatic sensing algorithm.

TABLE I
COMPLEXITY COMPARISON

Component	Joint 2D ESPRIT [3]	Proposed
EVD size	$L_f N_U = 3564$	$L_f = 396$
Dominant EVD cost	$(L_f N_U)^3 \approx 4.5 \times 10^{10}$	$L_f^3 \approx 6.2 \times 10^7$
Spatial EVD	(included)	$\tilde{K} L_s^3 = 192$
ZF projection	—	$\mathcal{O}(M \tilde{K}^2)$
Reduction	$1 \times$	$\sim 730 \times$

Parameters: $L_f = 396$, $N_U = 9$, $L_s = 4$, $\tilde{K} = 3$, $M = 792$.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Setup

The system operates at $f_c = 28$ GHz with $\Delta f = 120$ kHz, $M = 792$ subcarriers (bandwidth $W \approx 95$ MHz), and $P = 14$ OFDM pilot symbols. The BS has a 4×4 URA ($N_{B,x} = 4$, $N_{B,y} = 4$, $N_B = 16$) and the UE a 3×3 URA ($N_{U,x} = 3$, $N_{U,y} = 3$, $N_U = 9$). Without loss of generality, the BS is fixed at $\mathbf{p}_{BS} = [0, 0]^T$ m and the UE is randomly positioned at a fixed 20 m distance from the BS. Two passive targets with $\sigma_{RCS,1} = \sigma_{RCS,2} = 5$ m² are also randomly placed in the environment.

Two methods are compared: (i) the proposed decoupled algorithm and (ii) DFT baseline (zero-padded IFFT for ToF followed by 2D FFT beamforming for AoA). The CRB is computed via the Fisher information matrix (FIM) for the ToA-AoA estimation problem [13] and transformed to position coordinates using the Jacobian of the geometric mapping in (15)–(17). Impacts of SNR, signal bandwidth, UE array size, and number of OFDM symbols on positioning accuracy of the UE and the targets are separately evaluated through extensive 1000 Monte Carlo trials. Geometry is randomly generated in each iteration. Throughout the evaluation, UE RMSE is computed over all trials. Target RMSE is computed over all successfully detected target estimates. Table II reports the detection rate, defined as the ratio of valid target estimates to the total number of ground-truth targets ($2 \times 1000 = 2000$).

TABLE II
TARGET DETECTION RATE OF THE PROPOSED MDL-ESPRIT

Parameter	Value	Detection Rate (%)
SNR (dB)	0	90.6
	10	96.7
	20	99.3
	30	99.9
Bandwidth (MHz)	50	84.8
	100	93.7
	200	94.7
	400	95.2
UE Array Size	3×3	93.1
	4×4	94.1
	5×5	94.8
	6×6	95.4
OFDM Symbols (P)	1	88.2
	2	90.4
	4	92.8
	14	93.1
	28	92.9

B. Impact of SNR on Positioning Accuracy

Fig. 3 shows the UE and target localization RMSE over an SNR range of 0 to 30 dB, where $\text{SNR} = \sigma_s^2 / \sigma_n^2$ is the per-symbol receive SNR prior to coherent averaging. The 2D-FFT baseline exhibits a flat error floor of approximately 5.6 m for the UE and 13 m for the targets across the entire SNR range. It results from the Fourier grid spacing which brings a hard resolution limit in both the delay and angular domains. In contrast, the proposed method breaks this grid limitation. As shown in the logarithmic scale, the target RMSE of the proposed algorithm steadily converges toward the CRB, demonstrating its super-resolution estimation feature.

The baseline reports a near-100% detection rate across all SNR levels. However, this metric is uninformative as the algorithm always extracts a fixed number of spectral peaks regardless of the true target count. The corresponding 13 m

Fig. 3. Localization RMSE vs. SNR, comparing the proposed MDL-ESPRIT, the 2D-FFT baseline, and the theoretical CRB.

Fig. 4. CDF of localization error vs. SNR, comparing the proposed MDL-ESPRIT and the 2D-FFT baseline.

RMSE confirms that these detections are dominated by false-positive noise associations. In Table II, the MDL criterion in the proposed method achieves a 99.9% detection rate at 30 dB, rising from 90.6% at 0 dB, as the signal subspace becomes reliably separated from the noise subspace.

The empirical Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) in Fig. 4 further proves the above analysis. The proposed method concentrates probability mass below 0.1 m at high SNR, whereas the baseline exhibits a heavy right tail throughout the SNR range.

C. Impact of Signal Bandwidth on Positioning Accuracy

Fig. 5. Localization RMSE vs. Bandwidth, comparing the proposed MDL-ESPRIT, the 2D-FFT baseline, and the theoretical CRB.

Fig. 6. CDF of localization error vs. Bandwidth, comparing the proposed MDL-ESPRIT and the 2D-FFT baseline.

Bandwidth governs the delay-domain resolution and hence the ability to separate multipath components whose path-length difference is smaller than c/W . Fig. 5 sweeps the nominal bandwidth from 50 MHz to 400 MHz at SNR = 10 dB.

At 50 MHz the 2D-FFT baseline cannot resolve the two targets within a single range bin, leading to a collapse in target RMSE that exceeds 14 m. Performance improves progressively as bandwidth increases, consistent with the $1/W$ scaling of the Fourier resolution limit. The proposed method is practically insensitive to this sweep. By leveraging the subspace rotation-invariance feature of ESPRIT, the algorithm resolves targets separated by less than one Fourier bin independently of the system bandwidth. Consequently, the target RMSE remains strictly below 1.76 m across all tested values. This robustness has direct implications for bandwidth-limited 5G deployments where the full mmWave allocation may not be available to a sensing function.

The target RMSE of the proposed algorithm falls below the UE RMSE. This is because the UE position is determined only by the LoS path, whose range accuracy is directly governed by bandwidth. However, the target metric is computed only over successfully detected paths. As Table II confirms, the detection rate exceeds 94% at bandwidths above 100 MHz, indicating that this effect decreases as bandwidth increases.

The CDFs in Fig. 6 confirm that the proposed method achieves consistent tail behavior regardless of bandwidth, while the baseline's UE localization error distribution shifts between 50 MHz and 400 MHz.

D. Impact of UE Array Size on Positioning Accuracy

The receive aperture sets the angular resolution limit, which in turn governs how well the per-path AoA components can be separated in Stage 3. Fig. 7 reports RMSE as the UE URA scales from 3×3 to 6×6 elements.

For the baseline, a 3×3 array produces target RMSE exceeding 13 m because the 3 dB beamwidth of the small aperture is wider than the angular separation between the two targets. The proposed method achieves sub-1.5 m target RMSE even at 3×3 , since the spatially smoothed covariance matrix constructed in Stage 3 preserves the subspace structure required by ESPRIT. Target RMSE continues to fall as the

Fig. 7. Localization RMSE vs. UE array size, comparing the proposed MDL-ESPRIT, the 2D-FFT baseline, and the theoretical CRB.

array grows to 6×6 , tracking the CRB. It is caused by the improvement of the count of effective spatial snapshot and the angular separation introduced by additional antennas.

UE localization RMSE for the proposed method is near-constant beyond 4×4 . The UE positions itself via the direct LoS delay in Stage 4. As the array aperture grows, the bearing component of the position error eventually becomes negligible relative to the range component. At this point, further aperture growth provides no additional benefit, because the irreducible error floor is strictly bounded by the delay resolution of the $W \approx 95$ MHz bandwidth.

E. Impact of the Number of OFDM symbols on Positioning Accuracy

Fig. 8. Localization RMSE vs. number of OFDM symbols, comparing the proposed MDL-ESPRIT, the 2D-FFT baseline, and the theoretical CRB.

Fig. 8 evaluates performance as the number of OFDM pilot symbols varies from $P = 1$ to $P = 28$. The 2D-FFT baseline is insensitive to P , since coherent symbol averaging enters only as a scalar noise reduction factor σ_n^2/P and the Fourier resolution is unaffected.

The proposed method benefits from increasing P through the P -fold noise suppression in (7), but the more important contribution is the rank stabilization of the frequency-smoothed covariance matrix \mathbf{R}_f as the residual noise variance decreases. Target RMSE reaches 1.21 m at $P = 14$, the 5G NR slot length for numerology 3, and no further improvement is observed at $P = 28$. This rapid convergence results from the smoothing techniques in Stage 1 and Stage 3. Smoothing

restores covariance matrix rank even from a single-symbol observation by exploiting the structure of the URA.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We proposed a decoupled super-resolution ToF-AoA estimation framework for joint UE and target localization in bistatic MIMO-OFDM ISAC systems. By decomposing the estimation into sequential 1D frequency-domain ESPRIT, zero-forcing temporal projection, and per-path 2D spatial ESPRIT stages, the proposed algorithm achieves approximately three orders of magnitude reduction in computational complexity compared to the joint 2D ESPRIT, while maintaining super-resolution accuracy that significantly outperforms 2D-FFT baseline. The fully autonomous MDL-based model order detection excludes the need for manual parameter tuning. Future work includes extending the framework to involve Doppler estimation for moving targets and deriving the analytical CRB for the complete bistatic positioning problem.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Liu, Y. Cui, C. Masouros, J. Xu, T. X. Han, Y. C. Eldar, and S. Buzzi, "Integrated sensing and communications: Toward dual-functional wireless networks for 6g and beyond," *IEEE journal on selected areas in communications*, vol. 40, no. 6, pp. 1728–1767, 2022.
- [2] Y. Lyazidi, J. Equi, R. Shreevastav, I. Siomina, and G. Fodor, "Isac architecture and sensing topology switching in 6g cellular networks," in *2024 IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (CSCN)*, pp. 26–31, IEEE, 2024.
- [3] A.-J. van der Veen, M. Vanderveen, and A. Paulraj, "Joint angle and delay estimation using shift-invariance techniques," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 405–418, 1998.
- [4] Z. Zhou, J. Fang, L. Yang, H. Li, Z. Chen, and R. S. Blum, "Low-rank tensor decomposition-aided channel estimation for millimeter wave mimo-ofdm systems," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 35, no. 7, pp. 1524–1538, 2017.
- [5] M. Haardt, F. Roemer, and G. Del Galdo, "Higher-order svd-based subspace estimation to improve the parameter estimation accuracy in multidimensional harmonic retrieval problems," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 56, no. 7, pp. 3198–3213, 2008.
- [6] P. Maity, S. Srivastava, A. K. Jagannatham, and L. Hanzo, "Joint angle and velocity-estimation for target localization in bistatic mmwave mimo radar in the presence of clutter," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 73, no. 10, pp. 9846–9860, 2025.
- [7] Z. Xiao, R. Liu, M. Li, Q. Liu, and A. L. Swindlehurst, "A novel joint angle-range-velocity estimation method for mimo-ofdm isac systems," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 72, pp. 3805–3818, 2024.
- [8] V. P. Gil Jiménez and A. Gameiro, "Compact bistatic iterative passive radar based on terrestrial digital video broadcasting signals," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 15, no. 7, 2025.
- [9] M. Wax and T. Kailath, "Detection of signals by information theoretic criteria," *IEEE Transactions on acoustics, speech, and signal processing*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 387–392, 1985.
- [10] Y. Zhang, H. Chen, P. Zheng, B. Ning, H. Niu, H. Wymeersch, and T. Y. Al-Naffouri, "Joint bistatic positioning and monostatic sensing: Optimized beamforming and performance tradeoff," *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 2834–2847, 2025.
- [11] T.-J. Shan, M. Wax, and T. Kailath, "On spatial smoothing for direction-of-arrival estimation of coherent signals," *IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 806–811, 1985.
- [12] R. Roy and T. Kailath, "Esprit-estimation of signal parameters via rotational invariance techniques," *IEEE Transactions on acoustics, speech, and signal processing*, vol. 37, no. 7, pp. 984–995, 1989.
- [13] L. Pucci, L. Arcangeloni, and A. Giorgetti, "Position and velocity estimation accuracy in mimo-ofdm isac networks: A fisher information analysis," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2507.01743*, 2025.